

PROPAGATION OF COVID-19 INFORMATION ON FACEBOOK: A SOCIAL NETWORK ANALYSIS

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Introduction

Social media is accessed by an ever-increasing number of individuals worldwide. The most popular social media in terms of users is Facebook; according to Statistica, it is estimated to be 3.6 Billion as of the end of 2020 and projected to reach nearly 4.5 billion by 2025 (Clement, 2020).

There are three main concepts which revolve across Facebook and its user interactions: Users, Groups and Pages. When considering mainstream media, TV and Radio News Broadcast channels were often considered the main reliable news source in the past. At present, they have been overshadowed by Facebook pages or groups which have large followings or likes.

On social media, fake news or misinformation poses unique issues. Firstly, fake news is purposefully created to deceive readers, making it difficult to detect based on content alone. Secondly, most of the time, social media data is large-scale, multi-modal, primarily user generated, unidentified and noisy at times. Thirdly, social media users come from a variety of backgrounds, have varying tastes or demands, and utilize the platforms for a variety of purposes. Finally, the low cost of creating social media accounts makes it simple to create harmful accounts such as cyborg users, social bots and trolls, all of which can serve as strong sources of fake news (Shu, Bernard and Liu, 2018). With the outbreak of the COVID-19 pandemic, a surge in fake news has been observed, leading to people seeking out unproven medical remedies.

Facebook contains a considerable amount of information about its members and their relationships. Special graph-based mining techniques that can easily simulate the structure of social networks are required to assess and mine relevant information from these massive social network data sets (Akhtar, 2014). Regular quantitative statistical analysis tools have not effectively gained insight into the spread of fake news. In one case, the researchers used Social Network Analysis (SNA) approach to assess the distribution path of fake news on Facebook, measuring Degree Centrality, Closeness Centrality and Betweenness Centrality. The goal of the spread pattern analysis is to determine which regions are impacted by the harmful effects of fake news on social media (Ginting, *et. al.*, 2018).

The purpose of this exploratory study will be to understand how reliable information related to the Covid-19 pandemic is propagated through the popular Facebook pages and groups in Sri Lanka.

Based on the initial study, this research aims to address the following research questions:

1. What pages in Sri Lanka have contributed to the sharing of Covid-19 related verified information?
2. Is there a spread path for Covid-19 verified information in Sri Lanka pages and groups on Facebook?
3. What are the dominant pages, groups or communities who have shared verified Covid-19 related information?

Methodology

The approach proposed in this research is a mixed method (Qualitative + Quantitative Approach). The population under consideration is Facebook pages and groups related to Sri Lanka. The sample considered is posts published originally by a verified page related to Sri Lanka. The posts published from 1st January 2020 to 8th March 2021 are considered.

The approach to Data collection included the use of primary data obtained from Facebook. The researcher gained access to public data on Facebook pages provided for research purposes by Facebook CrowdTangle. This data is non-personal in nature. (i.e. this will not contain any personal information related to a profile). In order to analyze the data, Social Network Analysis was used. Data were pre-processed using Microsoft Excel. The Visualization Tool Gephi is considered for advanced analysis.

Results and Discussions

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Page Name	Total Interactions	Interaction Rate	Avg. Posts Per Day	Views on Owned Videos	Page Followers	Growth % and #
Average Total	517,230.83	0.902%	1.00	5.30M	163,339.33	+378.65%
1 Health Promotion Bureau	2.28M	1.327%	1.4	13.28M	514,870	+884.74% +462,585
2 UNICEF Sri Lanka	538,600	0.451%	0.82	14.00M	361,171	+15.70% +49,000
3 WHO Sri Lanka	181,588	1.95%	1.52	2.89M	26,366	+1,260.47% +24,428
4 National Blood Transfusion Service - Sri Lanka	42,472	0.804%	0.55	5,225	28,470	+80.18% +12,669
5 UNDP Sri Lanka	41,671	0.288%	1	1.58M	37,741	+30.82% +8,892
6 National Institute of Mental Health, Sri Lanka	18,157	0.594%	0.73	69,081	11,418	—

Figure 1: Verified Facebook Pages that Post Information About Covid-19.

Five health professionals in community medicine were interviewed to ascertain the Facebook pages which carry verified health information. Figure-1 shows the interactions carried out by the identified pages during the period of study as revealed by Crowdtangle. The highest interactions were for posts published by the Health Promotions Bureau (HPB). Next, using Crowd Tangle, a search and filtration was carried out to identify which pages and public groups have shared HPB Posts between the 1st of January 2020 to the 8th of March 2021. This was consistent with the process

followed by other researchers (Bruns *et. al.*, 2020). The end objective we hoped to match by this was to identify what Facebook pages share verified covid-19 related posts most and the influential spread pages and public groups.

Page Name	Total Posts	Total Interactions
Gotabaya Rajapaksa	29	6478
Emasha Hans	1	1933
Mobitel	6	1900
Government Medical Officers' Association	13	1710
Azzam Ameen	3	1318
Dr Nalinda Jayatissa	14	1160
Namal Rajapaksa	3	1131
Natasha Rathnayake	1	1049
කලීකාර සිත් අරණ	84	920
Palitha Thewarapperuma	4	873
මකාරේකා ගැන ඇත්ත දැනගන්න-COVID19 Fact Checker	23	695
NO PMC - For Free Education	16	607
Campus Set Eka/කැම්පස් අපේ පිටුව	2	580
සිංදු පොත (sindu potha)	2	580
Angajan Ramanathan	50	531

Figure 2: Facebook Pages and Groups with the Most Interactions

Ginting, Manongga and Sembiring (2018) have conducted a study analysis of the spreading path of Hoax news on Facebook using SNA. They explained that the higher amount of closeness centrality means those users (nodes) are capable of spreading information more. Consequently they found a list of users capable of spreading more information. In this research, we identified a list of 15 pages and groups (Figure 2) which have the most interactions with HPB based on their high closeness centrality. (Capability of spreading verified covid-19 related information).

Further, the research by Ginting, Manongga and Sembiring (2018) identified that a higher amount of betweenness centrality indicates those nodes have more power to control information and manage the information path between nodes. In this study by using the Gephi Visualization Tool, we identified the following 10 Facebook pages and groups which are responsible for sharing more posts of the HPB than the other pages and groups:

1. DMC Sri Lanka
2. Embassy of Sri Lanka in Havana
3. A Professionals' Forum
4. Angajan Ramanathan
5. Sri AV TV
Network
6. SF 2020
7. Trincomalee
8. Umi Baby Food
9. (Thulawa) Justice
10. Kawaraya

They may not get more interactions due to audiences, but still, they increasingly spread the information to others. Using the Betweenness centrality measurement calculation assist to validate the above pages and groups. Further, it identifies which HPB URLs shared most of the pages and public groups.

Conclusion

In this study, we identify Health Promotion Bureau (HPB) page is responsible for sharing the most verified Facebook post in Sri Lanka. Further this study identifies who is responsible for carrying out spreading verified news related to the Covid-19 pandemic through the HPB page. Further, it reveals which pages can influence more audiences by sharing HPB posts.

The results of this study can be useful for Sri Lankan health professionals to identify which pages and public groups share more reliable information with others and which pages and public groups can influence more

audiences by sharing this verified information. This can further enable them to collaborate with those pages and public groups to spread more reliable health related information. It further helps people to know more about verified information, and also it helps to minimize the spreading of misinformation on covid-19.

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